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THEATER: A PERFORMING ART OF KNITTING EMOTIONS

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Abstract

Theater being and direct medium operates on human level with its audience. Though theater has always been facing upheavals and difficulties claiming for the audience but finally has a beauty of its own. The accomplishment that an artist and the director expect from the audience is only the curtain falling with a thunderous applause. Theater artists live in a world of their own and are fully passionate about their work. Theater is an art to be felt and experienced. Theater is a live medium of entertainment which engages its audience through creative expression. The artist has the inner picture of who he is playing. The live response of the audience makes it all worth for them.

With no cuts, no retakes, full on dressed in characters attire the performing artist and the man behind the curtain that is the director of the play puts in his heart and soul waiting for the feedback from the audience.

Key Words: Theatre, Artist, cut and retake

Introduction:

The vivid culture of India has always been a way of living of its people. Different languages, religions, dance forms, music, architecture, food differing from place to place adds to the beauty of our country. It is therefore also referred to as the amalgamation of various cultures.

India's drama and theater has a long vivid heritage. In ancient India it was an important medium of communication. The Indian theater has a glorious history going way back to atleast 5000years. Kalidasa's play like 'Shakuntala' and 'Meghadoota' are few of the older dramas following those

of bhasa. These dramas are immortal in the minds of Indian audience. Kutiyattam of Kerala is one of the oldest surviving theater traditions of the world and goes back way to almost 2000 years old. Drama has always been an important means of mass communication.

Natyashastra by Bharat Muni is a text which tried to depict the mind of the performing artists for the very first time in Indian drama. It is acclaimed to be the earliest book on dramaturgy anywhere in the world. According to this epic a theater group should have persons specialized in seventeen types of works like: a) Bharata means the producer or the one who can perform everything related to a production. b) Vidusaka meaning a multi dimensional person who can make people laugh, c) Nata the person who perform as an actor –dancer, d) Sutradhara is further the person who is specialized in song and music during the performance, e) Natyakara is the one who according to Natyashastra expresses various rasas and bhavas natural to the people through different

character, f) Nandi is the person praising in Sanskrit, g)Nayakais the person engaged in the direction of dance during performance, h)Mukutkara the person who is responsible for the making of head gear for the required character, i)Veskara the person who is engaged in making costumes for the drama, j) Abharanakara person who has been assigned the duty of making ornaments for performance, k)Chitrakara rthe person given the task of painting for the performance, l)Rajaka the one responsible for cleaning the costumes, m)Karukara is the person engaged in decorating hall with wooden idols and sculpture, n)Kusilava person who can not only dance but also play musical instrument during the performance.

This list undoubtedly helps us in understanding the basic components of a theater group. The twenty seventh chapter of Natyashastra reveals that the actors acclaimed their performance to be successful by the immediate feedback of the audience and the parameter of this achievement was of two types human and divine. Theater in India has encompassed all the other forms of literature and fine arts into its physical presentation like literature, mime, music, dance, painting, sculpture and architecture- all merged into one art form: theater.

The parameter of acclaiming success in the current times is still the same but because of dearth of funds and onslaught of technology, theater in India now has a paradoxical image. Theater which has always been an institution since times immortal in the heart and soul of different

cultures of world cultures millennia now is confronting unprecedented challenges in today's e-society. Digital technologies and internet have spawned an array of media. The exodus from theater to technology is ironical but one also needs to realize that these are two different art forms.

With no cuts, no retakes, full on dressed in characters attire the performing artist and the man behind the curtain that is the director of the play puts in his heart and soul waiting for the feedback from the audience. Theater being and direct medium operates on human level with its audience. Though theater has always been facing upheavals and difficulties claiming for the audience but finally has a beauty of its own. The accomplishment that an artist and the director expects from the audience is only the curtain falling with a thunderous applause.

Theater artists live in a world of their own and are fully passionate about their work. Theater is an art to be felt and experienced. Theater is a live medium of entertainment which engages its audience through creative expression. The artist has the inner picture of who he is playing. The live response of the audience makes it all worth for them.

Objective & Research Methodology:

On the basis of study conducted in the Department of Communication Management and Technology of Guru Jambheshwar University of Science and Technology, Hisar it was revealed that art forms like theater are struggling hard for their survival as one of the objectives of the study was to find out that has technology affected traditional ways of entertainment like theater? The study basically an empirical one was conducted in Haryana-one of the smallest but prosperous states of the Indian union. For this four cities of Haryana -Karnal, Adampur, Hisar and Gurgaon representing the state were selected. Further a sample of 300 respondents representing (75 from each city) which serves the purpose of study was selected. However the actual responses received were 295 (Adampur 75, Gurgaon and Hisar 73 each and Karnal 74) and this constituted the universe of the study. The researcher resorted to purposive sampling but age, profession were kept in mind. Age of the respondent was further divided into parts (a) below 20 years (b) in between 20 to 30 years (c) above 30 years. In this study the respondents

were asked as to how technology has affected the traditional ways of communication like theater. The response of the respondents is depicted through the following table:

Analysis:

Do you think introduction of technology has affected traditional ways of entertainment like theater?

			Do you think introduction of technology has affected traditional ways of entertainment like theater etc?		Total
			No	Yes	
Age group of respondents	Below 20 years	Count	19	54	73
		% of Total	6.4%	18.3%	24.7%
	20-30 Years	Count	14	71	85
		% of Total	4.7%	24.1%	28.8%
	Above 30 years	Count	43	94	137
		% of Total	14.6%	31.9%	46.4%
Total		Count	76	219	295
		% of Total	25.8%	74.2%	100.0%

As it is visible from the above table that when the respondents were asked that has the introduction of technology affected traditional ways of entertainment like theatre almost 219(74%) respondents responded that introduction of technology has affected traditional ways of entertainment like theatre, whereas 76(25.8%) respondents said that folk art has a specific audience and therefore introduction of technology has not affected traditional ways of entertainment like theatre.

In the age group of below 20 years 54(18.3%) respondents responded that introduction of technology has affected traditional ways of entertainment like theatre whereas 19 (6.4%) respondents responded that introduction of technology has not affected traditional ways of entertainment like theatre. Further in age group of 20-30 years 71(24.1%) respondents responded that introduction of technology has affected traditional ways of entertainment like theatre whereas 14 (4.7%) respondents responded that introduction of technology has not affected traditional ways of entertainment like theatre. Finally in the age group of above 30 years 94(31.9%) respondents responded that introduction of technology has affected traditional ways of entertainment like theatre whereas 43(14.6%) respondents responded that introduction of technology has not affected traditional ways of entertainment like theatre. Thus to sum up the above diagram it can be said that although technology has affected traditional ways of entertainment but still there will always be an audience for theater who is still connected to it.

Conclusion:

Thus it is visible from the above graph that though onslaught of technology has affected traditional ways of entertainment like theater but theater will always have its own share of

audience as it has always been a timeless art form but has gradually been losing its audience. Also the problem with the theater industry lies in funding. Though technology has also undoubtedly occupied the entertainment industry but though for some theater has its own charm. Theater has undoubtedly been confronting unprecedented challenges from the lucrative world of technological picturisation where they have too many entertainment choices on screen but it can always defy its critics by actively engaging its audience. The breathlessness that an actor upholds with tremulous fragility is what upholds the theater. Discipline, team work, time management, consistent hard work and above all presence of mind are what it takes to perform on stage. In the words of Ruch who said this in context of theater -“human beings creating and experiencing a story together in a room- that is not going away”. The whole team rehearsing for months and coming out every night to give a wonderful show, such culture should definitely be preserved and allowed to flourish. Theater is the only institution which has not succumbed because of its tough and devoted people to keep it alive. Though a less number but there will always be an audience for theater, and the best way to revitalize is to constantly support it and introduce it to people at a very young age to its wonderful journey.

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